

FEATURES OF THE APPLICATION OF APPLIED ART OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE ARCHITECTURAL AND DESIGN SOLUTION OF MODERN HOTELS

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Abstract. *The actual number of hotels on the earth is unknown to any tourism analysts. because they are both too many and are simultaneously getting worse. However, we won't write about it right now. The "stars" of hotels are the focus of today. Organizations with a special certificate that rate the standard of hotels award "stars" based on a number of criteria. The diversity of amenities and services provided comes first on the list of priorities. Then, the size of the rooms and the service alternatives, including restaurants, bars, saunas, and swimming pools, as well as guarded parking spaces, taxi calling, international calling, and security cameras, are considered. This article offers feedback on the characteristics of the Uzbek Applied Art's use.*

Keywords: *hotels, modern, architecture, design, applied art, tourism.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ПРИКЛАДНОГО ИСКУССТВА УЗБЕКИСТАНА В АРХИТЕКТУРНО-ДИЗАЙНЕРСКОМ РЕШЕНИИ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ГОСТИНИЦ

Аннотация. *Фактическое количество отелей на земле неизвестно ни одному туристическому аналитику. потому что их слишком много и одновременно становится все хуже. Однако мы не будем писать об этом прямо сейчас. Сегодня в центре внимания «звезды» отелей. Организации со специальным сертификатом, оценивающие уровень отелей, присуждают «звезды» по ряду критериев. Разнообразие предоставляемых удобств и услуг стоит на первом месте в списке приоритетов. Затем рассматриваются размеры номеров и варианты обслуживания, включая рестораны, бары, сауны и бассейны, а также охраняемые парковочные места, вызов такси, международные звонки и камеры видеонаблюдения. В данной статье предлагается отзыв об особенностях использования узбекского прикладного искусства.*

Ключевые слова: *гостиницы, модерн, архитектура, дизайн, прикладное искусство, туризм.*

INTRODUCTION

The architecture of hotels today reflects practically all current architectural trends and flows. The hotel gives you the freedom to develop all of your creative ideas and an unforgettable image because it is so large and complicated and offers protective, social, and entertainment functions. For this, architects frequently use conventional planning techniques and building materials. Architects create an appealing and unforgettable image of the hotel complex by combining them with unexpected inventive concepts. Hotels can be categorized into three types based on their various architectural approaches: modern hotel complexes, hotels housed in old structures, and exotic hotels. Such hotels typically lack a national hue in their architectural design, creating a first-impression of modern architecture that influences the.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Also, the location of hotels has a great influence on their "star". It is advisable that the hotels are located in the city center or near the metro station. In Europe, however, the location close to the city's attractions is one of the main factors that positively affect the hotel's "star". The requirements for resort hotels are slightly different: the location of the hotel on the beach, the presence of its own coast, the presence of free beds and umbrellas improve their level. Personnel assessment is also of particular importance when issuing a "star". For example, an employee at a one-or two-star hotel receptionist must know at least one foreign language. In 4 or 5 Star hotels, however, you should be able to speak 4 languages fluently. Let's get acquainted with the requirements for each "star".

1. the simplest convenience. The location is not so significant. As a rule, the number of names in such hotels does not exceed 10. Their food is not taken into account, but if you pay for it, they can bring a modest breakfast. It is forbidden to enter the hotel after 1:00 at night.
2. for tourists, an excursion is offered, which is not so expensive. According to European and American standards, the room will have a toilet, bathroom and TV, but it is necessary to pay separately for the TV remote. There are no restrictions on admission to the hotel. Breakfast is usually served with kefir / yogurt, buns and coffee, butter, cheese, jam, sometimes hot dogs and eggs. In some, the restaurant is located in the Hall of a floor.
3. one of the common types of hotels. Soap and shampoo are always found in the bathroom, sometimes even a hairdryer. There is a phone and a TV, some have a mini-bar and air conditioning. The American 3-star hotel is considered almost equal to the European 4-star. In Turkey and Egypt, however, the room must be air-conditioned.
4. it is considered one of the types of hotels of the highest quality. These types of hotels will be located in the city center or along the coast. Also, guarded parking, Free Trainer halls, courts and pools, shows and Discos will determine its level. And it is important that the room has a toilet-bathroom (with a feni), air conditioning, a color TV with remote control, a refrigerator, a mini-bar, a mini-safe and a telephone for international calls. In fact, hotels of this type are practically no different from 5-star hotels, but the bosses do not chase after the "star" to avoid excessive taxes.

RESULTS

Having autonomy, such complexes make it possible to realize their needs for entertainment and carry out Rest In addition to relaxation. In addition, for the successful conduct of various business events, there are in such hotels - Congresses, Conferences, etc. Today, modern hotel complexes are closely connected with the entertainment industry. This trend can be seen on the example of hotels located in the territories of thematic amusement parks, such as Disneyland. In these conditions, the hotel will fit into the surrounding reality, which will turn into a stunning landscape with a spectacular view against the background. The architecture of the Las Vegas global gambling center is distinguished by the fact that attractions are included in the foundations of different countries. The tendency to save and restore old hotels can be observed almost all over the world. This is especially true in Europe, where many truly architectural monuments have been preserved. In the architecture of hotels, the tendency to look closely at history is most noticeable, and old buildings will have a new life. Historical cities with rich cultural traditions in European capitals and historical cities, such hotels are usually located close to other historical attractions. Hotels are distinguished by their architectural and planning forms, which are located among the natural landscapes located in tourist and well-being places. The

nature of the natural landscape is the choice of architectural forms, among which the following are distinguished:

1. the architectural forms corresponding to the landscape consist of four buildings in the form of hills in the form of hills in the hotel for tourists and athletes in Sweden;
2. against the landscape or relaxation architecture of a tourist hotel. According to this approach, two dominant parameters are used: the landscape - the first accent in the Crimea - The "Rock" Hotel in the Crimea, for example, expressed its size in facilitating a clear natural landscape;
3. presentation of Landscape Architecture-in this approach, natural forms of landscape and architectural forms are harmoniously combined. For example, the architecture of the StegiGenberger hotel Gstaad-Sean Hotel (Switzerland) with a complex of closed buildings of different heights, reflects the silhouette of the surrounding roofs.

DISCUSSION

Tourist and health centers are combined with various tourist institutions into tourist complexes. According to the specialty, the following tourist complexes are distinguished: youth tourist complex - a tourist hotel, which includes a tourist base, tourist camp; tourist and Sports Complex tourist hotel, tourist base, sports camp; mining and sports tourist complex tourist hotel, tourist base, ski station; water surface tourist complex tourist hotel, water base, water station.

The most important of them are located in a variant that reflects the architectural and historical significance of the buildings in the established urban development. Many hotels have existed for a long time and have their own history and traditions, proud of their famous guests. The level of comfort in them is at the highest level, since in the process of reconstruction and renewal they are equipped with modern engineering equipment. At the same time, the exterior and interior of the building were restored, the initial appearance was returned, the authenticity of the past period was restored. All decorations of interiors and such hotels are made in the style and traditions of a certain historical period. Similar hotels received world fame.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the hotel, which combines the achievements of national and modern architecture, has all the conditions for providing quality customer service. The equipment and items of the hotel, which embody our national crafts, traditions and traditions, will undoubtedly attract the attention of foreign tourists in particular. Many hotels have existed for a long time, have their own history and traditions and are proud of their famous guests. The level of comfort in them is at the highest level, since in the process of reconstruction and repair they are equipped with all modern engineering equipment. At the same time, the exterior and interior of the building were restored, they were returned to their original appearance, the original atmosphere of the past era was restored. The interiors and all the decoration of such hotels are created in accordance with the style and traditions of a particular historical era. Such hotels have become world famous.

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